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Effect Of Project Based Learning Strategy On Students Interest And Performance In Chemistry In Jalingo Education Zone Taraba State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study focuses on the effect of project based-learning strategy on students' interest and performance in chemistry in Jalingo Education Zone. Specifically, the objectives of the study were to; determine the mean score interest of Students taught Chemistry using the Project Based Learning Strategy in Jalingo Education Zone of Taraba State, Nigeria, compare the mean score interest of male and female students taught Chemistry using Project Based Learning Strategy in Jalingo Education Zone of Taraba State, Nigeria, determine the mean score Academic Performance of students taught Chemistry using Project Based Learning Strategy Compared to their counterparts taught same concepts using Guided Discovery in Jalingo Education Zone of Taraba State, Nigeria and Compare the Mean Score of Academic performance of male and female students taught Chemistry using Project Based Learning Strategy in Jalingo Education Zone of Taraba State, Nigeria. The study adopted quasi-experimental design with a samples size of two hundred and forty (240) Chemistry SS II students from secondary schools in the Jalingo Education Zone, Taraba State, which comprises of 150 males and 90 females selected from two (2) public secondary schools. The Student Chemistry Interest Inventory was the Instrument used for data collection. The instruments was subjected to validation by experts. With the reliability index of 0.99 established by Cronbach Alpha reliability method. Results of the study among others revealed that the SCII items have mean rating above 2.50 but below 3.50 including the grand mean which suggests that students developed interest in Chemistry when taught using Project Based Learning Strategy in Jalingo Education Zone of Taraba State. It was recommended that Chemistry Educators should maintain consistency and employ Problem-Based Learning Strategies (PBLs) in their instruction to stimulate student interest in the Jalingo Education Zone of Taraba State, Nigeria.

Keywords: Project based learning, Academic performance, Guided Discovery Strategy, Students Interest, & Instruction

INTRODUCTION

Recently, the advancement and global quest of sciences in our society has highlighted the difficulties in teaching and learning processes which necessitated research modifications to enhance students' engagement and performance in related courses such as Chemistry. Researchers like Fatokun et al. (2019) express that despite the recognized advantages of new teaching tactics and numerous initiatives for their implementation by science educators, traditional teaching methods continue to prevail in most science classes, including chemistry. As suggested by Isa et al. (2020) pointed that the transmission of knowledge necessitates educators to employ suitable methods and pedagogical approaches that align with the learners' interests, subject matter, and intended goals.

Impressively, to meet the demands of the 21st-century development and innovation in sciences, learners must engage with a project-based learning strategy in science and particularly in the field of chemistry. Goldsby and Raymond (2013) view Chemistry as one of the numerous fields of science. They noted further that it is frequently referred to as the mother of all sciences due to its relevancies to other scientific disciplines. The Study of Chemistry equipped students for professional jobs in several fields such as medical, biotechnology, agriculture, and pharmacy.

Pertinent to the foregoing, it necessitates an investigation to determine the most effective teaching approach for chemistry instruction in secondary schools in Jalingo Education Zone of Taraba State, Nigeria. Thus, the selected strategies are project based learning strategy and guided discovery methods. The paper will implore these strategies to investigate their effects on students' interest and performance in Jalingo Education Zone of Taraba State, Nigeria. Chiu (2020) observed that project-based learning (PBL) is a collaborative pedagogical method that immerses students in real-life scenarios for practical application. Even Bender (2012) encapsulates the essence of PBL by asserting that it involves collaborating to resolve a problem. In a report by Hassan et al. (2017) examined the impact of a project-based learning strategy on the achievement and interest of basic technology students in junior secondary schools in the Bida and Kontagora regions of Niger State, Nigeria. Sri (2014) sought to investigate student interest and motivation in project-based learning. The reports are not enough as their study do not include gender differences and students' performance that the present study seeks to determine.

Similarly, guided discovery method creates creative ability in students. It enables student transfer what he learnt in one concept to other concepts, thereby developing the student independent thought. Akanmu (2013) investigated on the effect of guided discovery learning strategy and senior secondary school students' performance in mathematics in Ejigbo, Nigeria. It was found that there is significant difference in favour of those exposed to guided discovery learning strategy compared to those not taught using guided discovery learning strategy. According to the researcher, both male and female performed equally well when taught using guided discovery strategy.

In line with the above, the researchers presently consider academic performance and interest among secondary school students in Jalingo Education Zone, Taraba State. Caballero et al. (2015) perceive students' academic performance as the process of fulfilling the aims, achievements, and objectives established in the program or course undertaken by a student. In the other hand, Adeleye (2011) defines interest as the inclination to engage in an activity. In this study, interest refers to the curiosity to examine Chemistry. These two variables (Academic Achievement and Students interest) are studied based on gender differences of male and female students in Jalingo Education Zone. Research conducted by Hassan et al. (2017) revealed that both male and female students attained high levels of accomplishment due to the implementation of Project-Based Learning in Basic Technology. Also, Godpower-Echie and Ihenko (2017) conducted a study on the impact of gender on students' interest and academic performance in Integrated Science within the Obio Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State. The results indicated that gender significantly affects interest but does not significantly impact the achievement of Integrated Science students. Eze et al. (2021) conducted a study on the gender-specific impact of the project-based learning technique on the academic achievement and retention of technical college students in Basic Electricity. Research indicated that male and female technical college students instructed in Basic Electricity through a project-based learning approach exhibited superior achievement and retention scores compared to those educated via guided discovery teaching methods.

Statement of the Problem

Chemistry is essentially important as a scientific discipline in Nigeria's secondary school curriculum. Despite its crucial role and influence in the sciences, a low level of interest and performance in chemistry is still a topic of concern to educators. This can be attributed to ineffective teaching methods that fail to engage students in the study of chemistry in secondary schools in Nigeria, including the Jalingo education zone.

It has been discovered that guided discovery methods, frequently employed in teaching chemistry topics (e.g. chemical combination) in Nigeria secondary schools is predominantly observed to be method where

students listen, copy, and passively receive information from teachers in the classroom. It does not facilitate meaningful learning of chemistry concepts in the classroom environment.

The 2019 report by the West African Examination Council (WAEC) Chief Examiner indicated that the majority of applicants had poor performance in chemical combinations. The Chief Examiner emphasized that this may stem from candidates' challenges in comprehending the notion of chemical combination. The Chief Examiner indicated that applicants encountered significant problems in responding to questions concerning chemical bonding and water hardness (WAEC, Chief Examiner Report 2019). As students' progress and their class size expands, their interest in learning may increase (or decrease); nonetheless, other researches contend that gender significantly affects interest but does not substantially impact students' ability in science. This study aims to assess students' interests in relation to gender and performance. A gap remains in determining which learning technique is most effective for enhancing students' interest, performance, and retention. Gender differences exist among the students. This study examines the benefits of Project-Based Learning Strategy on students' interest and performance in Chemistry in Jalingo, Taraba State, Nigeria, based on prior contributions.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study is to determine the effects of project based learning strategy on students' interest, performance and retention in chemistry in Jalingo Education Zone Taraba State, Nigeria. The specific objectives of the study are as follows, to:

1. Determine the mean score interest of Students taught Chemistry using the Project Based Learning Strategy in Jalingo Education Zone of Taraba State, Nigeria.
2. Compare the mean score interest of male and female students in Chemistry taught Chemistry using Project Based Learning Strategy Jalingo Education Zone of Taraba State, Nigeria.
3. Determine the mean score Academic Performance of students taught Chemistry using Project Based Learning Strategy Compared to their counterparts taught same concepts using Guided Discovery in Jalingo Education Zone of Taraba State, Nigeria.
4. Compare the Mean Score of Academic performance of male and female students taught Chemistry using Project Based Learning Strategy in Jalingo Education Zone of Taraba State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following Research questions are formulated to guide the study:

1. What is the mean interest score of Students taught Chemistry using the Project Based Learning Strategy in Jalingo Education Zone of Taraba State, Nigeria?
2. What is the mean interest score of male and female students taught chemistry using Project Based Learning Strategy in Jalingo Education Zone of Taraba State, Nigeria?
3. What is the mean score of Academic Performance of students taught chemistry using Project Based Learning Strategy and those taught same concepts using Guided Discovery in Jalingo Education Zone of Taraba State, Nigeria?
4. What is the mean score of Academic performance of male and female students taught chemistry using Project Based Learning Strategy in Jalingo Education Zone of Taraba State, Nigeria?

Review of Related Literature

Mabel and Williams (2019) who undertook a study on Students Attitude towards Chemistry and their Academic Achievement in Selected Concepts in Chemistry among Secondary School Students in Ibiono Ibom Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Findings revealed that as students' attitude towards Chemistry improved, achievement in chemistry increased significantly. Findings also showed that as male and female students' attitude towards chemistry taken together reduced, their achievement in chemistry improved. Bas (2011) who undertook a study on the Effects of Project-Based Learning on Students' Academic Achievement and Attitudes towards English Lesson. The results of the research showed a significant difference between the attitude scores of the experiment group and the control group Dominggus and Kristin (2019) examined the impact of project-based learning methodologies on the metacognitive skills, conceptual knowledge, and retention of senior high school students. The research findings indicated that the application of a project-based learning technique significantly impacted

students' metacognitive skills, conceptual understanding, and retention. Wekesa and Ongunya (2016) investigated Project Based learning on Students' Performance in the Concept of Classification of Organisms among Secondary Schools in Kenya. The study revealed that project-based learning technique enabled students to improve in academic achievement as well as developing positive attitude towards classification of organisms.

Al-Abdullatif and Gameil (2021) who conducted a study on the effect of Digital Technology Integration on Students' Academic Performance through Project-Based Learning in an E-Learning Environment. The finding suggested that TAM-related factors and students' learning engagement positively affect their academic performance when digital technology is integrated into the PBL environment. Jeffrey and Suleiman (2016) who conducted a study on Students' Personal Interest towards Project – Based Learning. Paired samples-t-test results showed that students' personal interest in each perspective have a statistically significant difference after PBL

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study adopted quasi-experimental design, namely a non-equivalent for pretest & posttest and control group design. The study was conducted in Jalingo education zone. The study population included 2,223 Chemistry students from 53 public secondary schools in the Jalingo education zone of Taraba State for the 2022/2023 academic year (MBSEDERC, 2023). The cohort of chemistry students comprised 1,601 males and 622 females. The study sample comprises two hundred and forty (240) Chemistry SS II students from secondary schools in the Jalingo Education Zone, Taraba State, including 150 males and 90 females selected from two (2) public secondary schools. The study employed a 30-item structured questionnaire, termed the Students Chemistry Interest Inventory (SCII), developed from Danjuma (2011), utilising a four-point Likert scale: Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD). It consists of 30 questions to assess students' interest. The Chemistry Performance Test (CPT) comprises 50 multiple-choice questions, each with alternatives A, B, C, and D, from which respondents must select one correct answer. The test items were sourced from the West African Examination Council. The CPT and SCII were taken to three experts for face and content validation; which gave an average agreement rate of 76% which means that the instruments are valid and suitable for data retrieval. A pilot test was carried out considering SS II students at Government Day Secondary School Lankaviri, located in Yorro Local Government Area of Taraba State, Nigeria. The participants, an intact class of 30 Chemistry students, were randomly selected for the pilot testing of the SCII and CPT. The analysis of instrument reliability of research instrument was conducted after obtaining data from the respondent test result, using Kuder-Richardson formula (KR-20). With reliability indexes of SCII was 0.97 and CPT was 0.99, indicating that the instruments are highly dependable. The mean and standard deviation were employed to address the research questions. Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the hypothesis.

RESULTS

This unit deals with the presentation of results of the statistical analysis of data gathered for the study as well as their discussion and interpretations. The presentation of the data was done following the research questions and hypotheses directing the study.

Research Question One: *What is the mean interest score of Students taught Chemistry using the Project Based Learning Strategy in Jalingo Education Zone of Taraba State, Nigeria?*

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviations ratings on the mean interest score of Students taught Chemistry using the Project Based Learning Strategy in Jalingo Education Zone of Taraba State, Nigeria

S/N	Statement	Mean	SD	Decision
1	I want to be carrying out chemistry activities	3.50	0.72	SA
2	I like using simple tools for chemistry activities	3.35	0.69	A
3	Chemistry lessons help me in solving problems at school	3.17	0.80	A
4	I look forward to doing assignments in Chemistry	3.16	0.79	A
5	I like carrying out chemistry activities	3.22	0.81	A
6	I am willing to spend a whole day studying chemistry.	3.35	0.88	A
7	I enjoy participating in chemistry Quiz	2.56	1.05	A
8	Solving problems in chemistry is interesting to me	3.30	0.82	A
9	I like to participate in chemistry activities	3.44	0.72	A
10	I can do most of the chemistry activities with little assistance	3.18	0.84	A
11	I feel sleepy when doing assignments in chemistry	3.42	0.76	A
12	Chemistry activities make me want to study science at secondary school	3.33	0.72	A
13	I can carry out some chemistry activities on my own	2.81	1.09	A
14	I like to watch chemistry teachers demonstrate some activities.	3.46	0.78	A
15	I like to do project work in chemistry.	3.44	0.72	A
16	I like to work with others in chemistry practical.	3.28	0.88	A
17	I think chemistry lesson is captivating	3.14	0.89	A
18	There is something captivating about chemistry lesson	3.30	0.76	A
19	I enjoy listing elements in chemistry lesson	3.31	0.84	A
20	I can now think of different ways to learn chemistry	3.31	1.26	A
21	To learn chemical equilibrium in chemistry i am encourage by instructional procedure	3.11	0.72	A
21	I can perform better in chemistry lesson	2.59	0.66	A
Grand Mean		3.12	0.75	A

Field survey, 2024 Criterion Mean: $X \geq 2.50 \Rightarrow A$; $X \leq 2.50 \Rightarrow D$

Results of Table 1 revealed the mean and standard deviation of the rating scale on the mean interest score of Students taught Chemistry using the Project Based Learning Strategy in Jalingo Education Zone of Taraba State, Nigeria. The results revealed that all the items have mean rating above 2.50 but below 3.50 including the grand mean. This suggests that all the respondents unanimously agreed to the items on the level of interest of Students taught Chemistry using the Project Based Learning Strategy in Jalingo Education Zone of Taraba State, Nigeria. The standard deviation scores on all the items are relatively low, a situation which suggests that the respondents have interest in Chemistry when taught using Project Based Learning Strategy in Jalingo Education Zone of Taraba State.

Research Question Two: *What is the mean interest score of male and female students in Chemistry taught chemistry using Project Based Learning Strategy in Jalingo Education Zone of Taraba State, Nigeria?*

Table 2: Interest score of Male and Female Students taught Chemistry Using PBLS Jalingo Education Zone of Taraba State.

Gender	N	Pre-test		Post-test		mean gain
		mean	std. dev	mean	std. dev	
Male	45	9.64	1.87	21.24	2.44	11.60
Female	35	9.95	2.02	19.70	5.109.75	
Mean diff		0.31		1.54		1.85

Results in Table 2 indicates that male students taught Project Based Learning Strategy had a pretest performance mean score of 9.64 with standard deviation of 1.87, while their female had pretest mean score of 9.95 with standard deviation of 2.02. The difference between the pretest performance scores of the experimental group and the control group is 0.31. After the effect of the pretest has been statistically removed, the posttest mean score of male students stands at 21.24, while that of their female is 19.70. The posttest standard deviation score of the male students is 2.44, while that of the female students is 5.10, an indication that the posttest scores of the male students are more homogeneous than that of the female students. The difference between the interest posttest mean score of the male and female students is 1.54 and in favor of the male students.

Research Question Three: *What is the mean score of Academic Performance of students taught chemistry using Project Based Learning Strategy in Jalingo Education Zone of Taraba State, Nigeria?*

Table 3: Mean Performance Scores and Standard Deviations of Students taught chemistry using Project Based Learning Strategy in Jalingo Education Zone of Taraba State, Nigeria and those taught using the Guided Discovery

Group	N	Pretest		Posttest		Mean gain
		mean	std. dev	mean	std. dev	
PBLS	45	9.78	2.02	20.56	3.88	10.78
GD	35	9.43	2.16	14.80	3.01	5.37
Mean difference		0.35		5.76		3.45

Key: PBLS = Project Based Learning Strategy

GD = Guided Discovery

Table 3 revealed that the group taught Chemistry using Project Based Learning Strategy had a pretest mean score of 9.78 with standard deviation of 2.02, while those in the conventional teaching method had pretest mean score of 9.43 with standard deviation of 2.16. The difference between the pretest scores of the Project Based Learning Strategy group and the Guided Discovery group is 0.35. After the effect of the pretest has been statistically removed, the posttest mean score of the students taught using the Project Based Learning Strategy stands at 20.56, with standard deviation of 3.88 while those taught using Guided Discovery had a mean of 14.80, with standard deviation of 3.01. The posttest standard deviation scores of the two groups (IM = 3.88 and LM = 3.01) indicate that the posttest scores of the groups are both homogeneous within the groups. The difference between the posttest means score of the students in the two groups is 5.76 and in favor of the group taught Chemistry using integrated teaching method.

The mean gain (that is, difference between the pretest and posttest mean scores) of students taught using Project Based Learning Strategy is 10.78, while that of those taught using lecture method is 5.37. The mean gain revealed that the group taught using Project Based Learning Strategy gained higher than the conventional teaching method group by 3.45. The implication of these results is that students taught using Project Based Learning Strategy have higher performance mean scores than their counterparts taught using conventional teaching method.

Research Question Four: *What is the mean score of Academic performance of male and female students taught chemistry using Project Based Learning Strategy in Jalingo Education Zone of Taraba State, Nigeria?*

Mean Performance Scores and Standard Deviations of Students taught chemistry using Project Based Learning Strategy in Jalingo Education Zone of Taraba State, Nigeria and those taught using the Guided Discovery

Table 4: Academic Performance of Male and Female Students Taught Chemistry Using PBLs in Jalingo Education Zone.

Scores by Gender				
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Boys	45	48.22	14.89988	2.48331
Girls	35	47.31	12.05921	1.50740

From the results above, it was indicated that 36 out of 80 students of the experimental group taught chemistry using PBLs in Jalingo Education Zone were girls and 45 students were boys shown 48.3125 and 47.2222 respectively. It means that girls' performance was better than boys' performance in the study area. The performance scored gain (48.22) of male is higher than that of the female students (47.31). Thus, the male students gained 2.48 performance scores higher than their female counterparts. This implies that male students gained higher than female students with use of Project Based Learning Strategy in teaching chemistry.

Hypothesis One

There is no significant difference between the interest score of students taught Chemistry using Project Based Learning and those taught the same concepts using Guided Discovery Method.

Table 5: One-way ANCOVA of Significant difference between the interest score of students taught Chemistry using Project Based Learning and those taught the same concepts using Guided Discovery Method.

Sources of Variation	Sum of Squares	df Square	Mean	F	Sig squared	Partial Eta
Corrected Model	750.99 ^a	2	360.49	29.62	0.00	0.42
Intercept	894.55	1	894.55	73.49	0.00	0.47
Pre-test	19.50	1	19.50	1.60	0.21	0.02
Method	676.74	1	676.74	55.60	0.00	0.40
Error	998.02	82	998.02			
Total	28793.00	85				
Corrected Total	1719.01	84				

a. R Squared = .419 (Adjusted R Squared = .405)

Table 5 is a one-way between group's analysis of covariance between the mean interest scores of students taught chemistry using Project Based Learning and those taught the same concepts using Guided Discovery Method. After adjusting for the pre-test scores, there is a significant difference between the two groups on students' interest scores $F(1,82) = 55.60, p = 0.00$, with large effect size (partial eta squared = 0.40). The effect size shows that 40% of the variance in interest scores of the students is based on the method of teaching (Project Based Learning) used. Thus, the hypothesis of There is no significant difference between the mean interest score of students taught Chemistry using Project Based Learning and those taught the same concepts using Guided Discovery Method is, hereby, rejected. That is, there is significant difference between the mean interest scores of students taught chemistry using Project Based Learning and those taught using Guided Discovery Method this indicates that the students taught chemistry using Project Based Learning have significantly better interest than those taught using Guided Discovery Method in Jalingo Education Zone.

Hypothesis Two

There is no significant difference between the mean interest score of male and female students taught chemistry using Project Based Learning Strategy in Table 8

Table 6: Tests of Between-Subjects Effect of Students' mean interest score of male and female taught chemistry using Project Based Learning Strategy.

Sources of Variation	Sum of Squares	df Square	Mean	F	Sig squared	Partial Eta
Corrected Model	39.32 ^a	2	19.66	1.32	0.28	0.06
Intercept	954.67	1	954.67	64.28	0.00	0.61
Pre-test	12.97	1	12.97	0.87	0.36	0.02
Gender	23.43	1	23.43	1.58	0.22	0.04
Error	623.79	42	14.85			
Total	19677.00	45				
Corrected Total	663.11	44				

a. R Squared = .059 (Adjusted R Squared = .014)

Results from Table 6 revealed a one-way between groups analysis of covariance of the mean interest scores of male and female students taught chemistry using Project Based Learning Strategy. After adjusting for the pre-test scores, there is significant difference between the interest scores of male and female students, $F(1,42) = 1.58$, $p = 0.05 = .05$. The effect size shows that 0.4% of variance in the interest scores of the students is attributable to the sex of the students. Thus, the hypothesis of There is no significant difference between the mean score interest level of male and female students taught chemistry using Project Based Learning Strategy is, hereby, rejected. That is, there is significant difference between the mean interest scores of male and female taught chemistry using Project Based Learning this indicates that the male students taught chemistry using Project Based Learning have significantly better interest than the female.

Hypothesis Three

H_{03} : There is no significant difference between mean performance scores of students taught Chemistry with Project Based Learning Strategy and those taught with Guided Discovery method in Jalingo Education Zone.

Table 7: One-way ANCOVA of Method of Teaching on Students' Performance

Sources of Variation	Sum of Squares	df Square	Mean	F	Sig squared	Partial Eta
Corrected Model	750.99 ^a	2	360.49	29.62	0.00	0.42
Intercept	894.55	1	894.55	73.49	0.00	0.47
Pre-test	19.50	1	19.50	1.60	0.21	0.02
Method	676.74	1	676.74	55.60	0.00	0.40
Error	998.02	82	998.02			
Total	28793.00	85				
Corrected Total	1719.01	84				

a. R Squared = .419 (Adjusted R Squared = .405)

Table 7 is a one-way between group's analysis of covariance to compare the mean performance scores of students taught chemistry using Project Based Learning Strategy and that taught using conventional teaching method. After adjusting for the pre-test scores, there is a significant difference between the two groups on students' performance scores $F(1,82) = 55.60$, $p = 0.00$, with large effect size (partial eta squared = 0.40). The effect size shows that 40% of the variance in performance scores of the students is based on the method of teaching (Project Based Learning Strategy) used.

Thus, the hypothesis is not significant difference between the mean Performance scores of students taught chemistry using Project Based Learning Strategy and those taught using conventional teaching method is, hereby, rejected. That is, there is significant difference between the mean performance scores of students taught chemistry using Project Based Learning Strategy and those taught Guided Discovery method this indicates that the students taught chemistry using Project Based Learning Strategy performed significantly better than those taught using conventional teaching method

Hypothesis Four

There is no significant difference between the mean score of Academic performance of male and female students taught Chemistry using Project Based Learning Strategy.

Table 8: Tests of Between-Subjects Effect of Gender on Students' Performance in chemistry

Sources of Variation	Sum of Squares	df Square	Mean	F	Sig squared	Partial Eta
Corrected Model	39.32 ^a	2	19.66	1.32	0.28	0.06
Intercept	954.67	1	954.67	64.28	0.00	0.61
Pre-test	12.97	1	12.97	0.87	0.36	0.02
Gender	23.43	1	23.43	1.58	0.22	0.04
Error	623.79	42	14.85			
Total	19677.00	45				
Corrected Total	663.11	44				

a. R Squared = .059 (Adjusted R Squared = .014)

Results from Table 8 indicates a one-way between groups analysis of covariance to compare the mean performance scores of male and female students taught chemistry using Project Based Learning Strategy. After adjusting for the pre-test scores, there is no significant difference between the performance scores of male and female students, $F(1, 42) = 1.58$, $p = 0.33 > .05$. The effect size shows that 0.4% of variance in the performance scores of the students is attributable to the sex of the students. Thus, the hypothesis of no significant difference between performance scores of male and female students taught chemistry using project based learning is here by retained.

DISCUSSION

This section is concerned with the discussion of findings.

The level of interest of Students taught Chemistry using the Project Based Learning Strategy in Jalingo Education Zone of Taraba State, Nigeria. The results reveals that all the items have mean rating above 2.50 but below 3.50 including the grand mean this suggests that students developed interest in Chemistry when taught using Project Based Learning Strategy in Jalingo Education Zone of Taraba State.

The findings are in agreement with Hassan, (2017) who found that the use of Project-based learning as a teaching method increased students' interest and achievement in Basic technology more than the conventional chalkboard method of teaching

The findings corroborate that of Jeffry and Suleiman (2016) who conducted a study on Students' Personal Interest towards Project – Based Learning. Paired samples-t-test results showed that students' personal interest in each perspective have a statistically significant difference after PBL. Based on their contributions, the study is similar to the present study in the sense that the researcher will investigate students' interest on PBL based on their gender in chemistry.

The findings of the study support that of Jimoh and Fatokun (2020) undertook a study on the Effect of Problem-Based Learning Strategy on Chemistry Students' Achievement and Interest in Mole Concept in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria. Findings revealed that students taught mole concept using PBL strategy perform better and expressed better interest than those taught using lecture method. PBL

improved the achievement of both male and female students equally but fostered more interest in male students.

Results reveal that that the posttest scores of the male students are more homogeneous than that of the female students. The difference between the interest posttest mean score of the male and female students is 1.54 and in favor of the male students.

The findings are in agreement with the work of Hassan (2017) investigated the Effects of Project Based Learning Approach on Achievement and interest of Basic Technology students in junior secondary schools in Bida and Kontagora Areas of Niger State, Nigeria. The male and female students' Achievement in experimental group increased highly as a result of the use of project-based learning. The study findings are in agreement with the study conducted by Carter (2016) who conducted a study on the traditional vs. project-based learning: the effects on student performance and motivation in honors level mathematics courses. The ANCOVA results showed a statistically significant difference between the mean performance of the PBL group and the mean performance of the TL group. Also, results were obtained when the mean performance of male students, as well as the performance of female students, was compared between the two groups, thereby revealing that PBL instructional method helped to improve student achievement in honors level mathematics courses.

The findings of this study is in line with what Alamry (2020) found out on the effectiveness of a rational behavioral emotive program in reducing test anxiety among university students with high academic achievement in Riyadh. The results showed statistically significant differences between the average scores of the experimental group students in the pre and posttests in favor of the posttest. There were statistically significant differences between the average scores of the two groups in the posttest of the scale in favor of the experimental group. Furthermore, there were no statistically significant differences between the average scores of the experimental group in the post and successive tests of the scale.

The findings of this study is in agreement with that of Timothy and Umoru (2019) who conducted a study on the effect of Project-Based Teaching Methods on Business Education Students' Academic Performance in Principles of Accounting in Universities in South-West, Nigeria. The study found among others that project based teaching method had positive effect on the academic performance of Business Education students in principles of accounting, there was a significant main effect of treatment of project –based on academic performance of universities Business Education students in principles of accounting ($F= 135.759$; $P = .000$) and that there was no significant gender effect of project -based method on academic performance of universities Business Education students in principles of accounting ($F= 20.356$; $P = 0.000$).

The findings of this study is in support with what Timothy and Umoru (2019) who conducted a study on the effect of Project-Based Teaching Methods on Business Education Students' Academic Performance in Principles of Accounting in Universities in South-West, Nigeria. The study found among others that project based teaching method had positive effect on the academic performance of Business Education students in principles of accounting, there was a significant main effect of treatment of project –based on academic performance of universities Business Education students in principles of accounting ($F= 135.759$; $P = .000$) and that there was no significant gender effect of project –based method on academic performance of universities Business Education students in principles of accounting ($F= 20.356$; $P = 0.000$).

Table 3 reveals that the group taught Chemistry using Project Based Learning Strategy the mean gain shows that the group taught using Project Based Learning Strategy gained higher than the conventional teaching method group by 3.45. The implication of these results is that students taught using Project Based Learning Strategy have higher performance mean scores than their counterparts taught using conventional teaching method.

The finding of this study is in agreement with the findings of Darren, (2016) who conducted a study on the Effect of Project-Based Learning on Student Performance: An Action Research Study. The objective of the study was to assess the effectiveness of a project-based learning curriculum model utilizing the course's learning outcomes as its foundation in university-level. Data analyzed found that the experimental group that engaged the project and took responsibility for the learning of their peers scored

significantly higher on the multiple-choice exam when compared to the control group. The finding of this study is not contrary to the findings of Wekesa and Ongunya (2016) investigated Project Based learning on Students' Performance in the Concept of Classification of Organisms among Secondary Schools in Kenya. The study revealed that project-based learning technique enabled students to improve in academic achievement as well as developing positive attitude towards classification of organisms. The findings of this study is in support of Al-Abdullatif and Gameil (2021) who conducted a study on the effect of Digital Technology Integration on Students' Academic Performance through Project-Based Learning in an E-Learning Environment. The finding suggested that TAM-related factors and students' learning engagement positively affect their academic performance when digital technology is integrated into the PBL environment.

The findings of this study are in accordance with that of Bas (2011) who undertook a study on the Effects of Project-Based Learning on Students' Academic Achievement and Attitudes towards English Lesson. The results of the research showed a significant difference between the attitude scores of the experiment group and the control group. On the other hand, it was also found out that project-based learning was more effective in the positive development of the students' academic achievement levels. It was further revealed that the students who were educated by project-based learning was more successful and had higher attitude levels towards the lesson than the students who were educated by the instruction based on student textbooks.

From the results revealed that the performance scored gain (48.22) of male is higher than that of the female students (47.31). Thus, the male students gained 2.48 performance scores higher than their female counterparts.

This result is not contrary to the work of Bojan, (2021) who undertook a study on the influence of project-based learning on student achievement in elementary mathematics education. Results of the study shows that students in the experimental group, who worked according to the model of project-based work, achieved better compared to students who worked in the usual way.

The result reveals from this study is not contrary to the findings of the study conducted by Mabel and Williams (2019) who undertook a study on Students Attitude towards Chemistry and their Academic Achievement in Selected Concepts in Chemistry among Secondary School Students in Ibiono Ibom Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. findings revealed that as students' attitude towards Chemistry improved, achievement in chemistry increased significantly. Findings also showed that as male and female students' attitude towards chemistry taken together reduced, their achievement in chemistry improved. In terms of school location, a reduced urban and rural students' attitude towards chemistry did not correspond to reduced chemistry achievement.

Nevertheless, these findings confirmed the study of Dominggus and Kristin (2019) studied on the influence of project-based learning strategies on the meta-cognitive skills, concept understanding and retention of senior high school student. Results showed that the implementation of project-based learning strategy had a significant effect on students' meta-cognitive skills, concept understanding, and retention. The results indicated that the learning stages of project-based learning strategy could empower the students' meta-cognitive skills, concept understanding, and retention.

CONCLUSIONS

The findings of this study clearly indicates that the Project Based Learning Strategy enhanced students' interest in Chemistry more than the Guided Discovery Method in the Jalingo Education Zone of Taraba State and the use of Project-Based Learning Strategy enhanced student performance in Chemistry within the Jalingo Education Zone of Taraba State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the conclusion drawn from the study, the following recommendations were made:

- i. Chemistry educators should maintain consistency and employ Problem-Based Learning Strategies (PBLs) in their instruction to stimulate student interest in the Jalingo Education Zone of Taraba State.
- ii. Trainees of chemistry educators should receive training on managing gender disparities in chemistry instruction to enhance student interest in the subject, extending beyond high school education in the Jalingo Education Zone in Taraba State.
- iii. Educators should diversify creative teaching methods to enhance students' performance in Chemistry education in Jalingo, Taraba State.

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